

Computational model for neutrophil swarming

Research conducted at Eötvös Loránd University in the framework of the Inflanet consortium

Introduction

The modelling concept described below is a general approach to understanding some of the details of the behaviour on the level of individual cells. In this context modelling means the computer simulation of the respective concentration fields as well as the trajectories of the simulated cells typically called particles in a computational (*in silico*) approach. Simulations represent a useful tool in understanding biological processes by allowing the investigation of the relevance of the various factors of the process through monitoring the parameters governing them. It is important to point out that, although the present model may look at the first sight a bit complex (as compared to simple algorithms typically used in simulations), it still represents a *highly oversimplified* version of what eventually takes place during neutrophil swarming. Also, it can be later *developed further* in order to include additional effects into the *framework described below*. The model is flexible. At first, we implemented its two-dimensional version, and its *extension to 3D was straightforward*.

Before going to microscopic details, we first describe the overall framework. We consider a “region” of tissue which has a simple-shaped damaged part in it, where the word damage stands for a part of the tissue which has been subject to some sort of inflammation-triggering influence (e.g., a cutting or presence of bacteria/antigens). The damaged area is a source of signalling molecules (chemoattractant) with which the cells interact (“cells” will be mostly used for “neutrophils”). In addition, the cells themselves can be a source of chemoattractant molecules to a degree depending on their state or activation.

An important aspect of our modelling was testing it by comparing its output with *experimental observations*. To do so, we also carried out *in vitro* experiments designed to be useful from the point of assessing the applicability of the model.

Model

In our series of simulations, we used as experimental reference our own *in vitro* setup (see below) which provided for us phase contrast videos of swarming neutrophils in a layer of gel in the presence of a globular source of fMLF molecules playing the role of a chemoattractant.

In order to account for several important specific features of the observations, the model has to integrate further essential ingredients: a) The chemoattractant molecules diffuse in the medium, so *their momentary concentration is described by a complex partial differential equation*, b) these molecules are produced by the cells and can *spontaneously decay*, c) under some conditions the relevance of *inhibitory molecules* comes into play, d) the role of the inhibitory molecules is described by a *nonlinear ordinary differential equation* and d) the direction of the momentary velocity of the cells depends on the *gradient of the chemoattractant* (they move towards higher concentration) and by a random perturbation being the result of the many complex processes taking place simultaneously during the migration of neutrophils.

There are several more factors to be considered, such as, for example, the initial and boundary conditions assumed for the concentration of the chemoattractant, the average

density of the neutrophils, the size of the system together with the number of grid points for which the chemoattractant concentration is calculated in an iterative manner, and so on.

The simulations have two major components: **(I)** Calculation of the concentrations of the chemoattractant and the inhibitor molecules and **(II)** updating the position of the particles (neutrophils).

(I) *The equations to be solved numerically are:*

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = D\nabla^2 c + f(c, R)$$

for the concentration of the diffusing chemoattractant and

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = g(c, R)$$

for the local rate of the expression of the inhibitor, where

$$f(c, R) = a \frac{1}{1 + (c_1/c)^n} \sum_{j=1}^M \left(\frac{1}{1 + (R/R_1)^m} - \lambda_c c \right) \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_j)$$

is a source/sink contribution to the chemoattractant concentration and

$$g(c, R) = b \frac{1}{1 + (c_2/c)^k} - \lambda_R R$$

determines the rate by which the inhibitor's concentration is changing in time.

The initial conditions used were $c(\mathbf{r}, t) = 0$ everywhere beyond the region of the source of the chemoattractant and was equal to 1 over the source. The Neumann boundary condition with zero value was assumed far from the disk-shaped region of the source.

The various parameters in the above expressions denote the following quantities:

- c : the concentration of the chemoattractant, D : the diffusion constant, λ_c : the decay constant of the chemoattractant, λ_R : the rate of the spontaneous decay of the inhibitor molecules, a : the maximum production rate of the chemoattractant, b : the maximum production rate of the inhibitor, c_1 : the dissociation constant for the activation of chemoattractant production, c_2 : the dissociation constant for the activation of the inhibitor production, R_1 : the dissociation constant for the inhibition of the chemoattractant production, k, m, n : the Hill coefficients, M : the number of cells, \mathbf{r} : the position vector
- By introducing dimensionless parameters, the number of independent parameters can be reduced to 4.

Method

The equations were solved numerically using the implicit scheme for the values of $c(\mathbf{r}, t)$

$$-\alpha_z c_{t+1}^S - \alpha_y c_{t+1}^B - \alpha_x c_{t+1}^W + \beta c_{t+1}^P - \alpha_x c_{t+1}^E - \alpha_y c_{t+1}^F - \alpha_z c_{t+1}^N = c_t^P + f_P \Delta t$$

where (except the boundaries)

$$\alpha_x = \frac{D\Delta t}{\Delta x^2}, \alpha_y = \frac{D\Delta t}{\Delta y^2}, \alpha_z = \frac{D\Delta t}{\Delta z^2}$$

$$\beta = 1 + \left(\frac{2}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{2}{\Delta y^2} + \frac{2}{\Delta z^2} \right) D\Delta t$$

and S, B, W, P, E, F and N denote the respective parts of the *elementary volume in the finite volume discretization method*. For the sake of simplicity (without losing generality) we used $\Delta t = \Delta x = \Delta y = \Delta z = 1$ since they enter in a combination of multiplicative expressions containing the diffusion coefficient D which is controlled to both ensuring convergence and reproducing observable behaviour.

(II) For a given distribution of the chemoattractant the *positions of the cells are updated according to the following expressions*:

Let \mathbf{r}_t^X be the position vector of a given cell X at time t . It is updated following the rules:

$$\mathbf{r}_{t+1}^X = \mathbf{r}_t^X + d\mathbf{r}_{t+1}^X$$

$d\mathbf{r}_t^X$ has three components:

- $d\mathbf{r}_{p_t}^X = p_{coef} \mathbf{v}_{t-1}^X$: accounts for the persistence of the motion. p_{coef} is the persistence coefficient. Here \mathbf{v}_{t-1}^X is simply the difference of the positions of the cell X at time steps $t-2$ and $t-1$
- $(1 - p_{coef}) d\mathbf{r}_{ran_t}^X$: adds some noise to the motion. $d\mathbf{r}_{ran_{x,t}}^X$, $d\mathbf{r}_{ran_{y,t}}^X$ and $d\mathbf{r}_{ran_{z,t}}^X$ are taken from the the uniform distribution of random values in the intervals $[-rand_x/2, rand_x/2]$, $[-rand_y/2, rand_y/2]$ and $[-rand_z/2, rand_z/2]$ respectively.
- $d\mathbf{r}_{att_t}^X = grad_t^X \mathbf{e}_t^X$: accounts for the contribution of the chemotactic strength $grad_t^X$, \mathbf{e}_t^X is the unit vector in the direction of increasing gradients of concentration.

Previous studies have established that this strength is a function of both the gradient and the concentration of chemoattractant sensed by the cell. Let q_t^X be the relative difference in concentration of the ligand across the cell.

$$q_t^X = \frac{\|\nabla c_t^X\|}{c_t^X}$$

Currently, we assume that: $grad_t^X = q_t^X$.

The expressions in (II) provide a straightforward way of updating the positions of the initially randomly placed cells. In this way we implemented a combination of obtaining *concentration values at discrete positions* in space and time and obtaining updated positions for the cells for *discrete time steps, but for continuous variables of their coordinates*.

In vitro experiments on neutrophils swarming

Cell cultures: Human neutrophil granulocytes were isolated in the laboratory of Balázs Enyedi at Semmelweis University, Budapest in accordance with institutional protocols. Cells were transferred to ELTE for microscopy experiments. For creating 3D neutrophil cultures, we mixed cells in type I collagen (Corning) to create collagen extracellular matrix gel (2.2 mg/ml). After gelation in the ring areas, we covered all gels with culture medium and transferred the dishes to the microscope for time-lapse videomicroscopy.

Microscopy: All experiments were performed on a Zeiss Axio Observer Z1 inverted microscope with Zeiss Plan Neofluar 10x objective. The microscope was coupled to a Zeiss Axiocam MRM CCD camera and equipped with a Marzhauser SCAN-IM powered stage. A Zeiss Colibri LED illumination system with 365 nm LED module was used with a 25HE reflector filter set for photoactivation experiments. During time-lapse videomicroscopy, the cell cultures were kept in a stage-top incubator (CellMovie), providing the required temperature and 5% CO₂ atmosphere. Time-lapse images were taken consecutively every 1 minute or 10 minutes, depending on the experimental setup.

Chemoattractant injection experiments: Neutrophil swarming was induced by injecting the chemotactic peptide fMLF directly into the collagen gel matrix containing 0.9 million cell/ml in the rings of cell culture dishes. For the injection of 1 μ l fMLF (40 μ M) we used standard micropipette tips (D10, Gilson) and subsequently the injected area was imaged by time-lapse videomicroscopy phase contrast images were collected in every 10 minutes for up to 48 hours.

Chemoattractant photoactivation experiments: Chemoattraction-driven neutrophil swarming was also induced by photoactivating the chemotactic peptide fMLF through photocleaving its inactive precursor caged fMLF (c-fMLF) by illumination with 365 nm light. Initially, c-fMLF was added to the culture medium in concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 10 μ M, depending on the experimental setup. Subsequently we applied 365 nm illumination (2544 μ W/mm²) across the culture dish in a cylindrical volume with a diameter of 200 μ m. We imaged an area in phase contrast mode and repeated imaging every minute for 1 hour.

Results

Since one of the main goals of our studies were to get information about the most relevant factors influencing the time development of the process of neutrophil swarming, we created video files displaying the spatio-temporal changes in the system we investigate. In addition to visualizing the changes we also calculated a few characteristic features of the phenomenon and presented these in the form of plots.

Figure 1. Still images from the video recordings of the *in vitro* experiments on neutrophil swarming. The white spots are human neutrophils. The video of the experiment shown on the left above shows how neutrophils - over a duration of 20 hours - tend to move towards and aggregate at the position where fMLF was previously injected. Video links: <https://youtu.be/ooRiqOLTJTA> and <https://zenodo.org/records/15483615>. The still image on the right corresponds to the experiment in which fMLF is released from its caged form within the area indicated by the white circle (duration is 3 hours). Video links: <https://youtu.be/dXE6oOg92YM> and <https://zenodo.org/records/15483615>

Figure 2. Still images from the videos visualizing the simulations of neutrophil swarming. The video of the simulation shown on the left above is available here: <https://youtu.be/d2xvGpBlnu0> and <https://zenodo.org/records/15483615>, while the one on the right can be seen here: <https://youtu.be/6v9EluKGO0U> and <https://zenodo.org/records/15483615>. The two videos show the same simulation corresponding to the experimental setup shown on the left side of Figure 2. The video on the left shows the swarming from “above”, while the one on the right visualizes the behaviour in 3-dimensions with the last five moves of the particles indicated by a ragged green line. The intensity of the orange background colour displays the level of the concentration of the chemoattractant.

A useful way of characterising the simultaneous and “targeted” motion of many neutrophils is calculating a quantity called *velocity autocorrelation function*. This function for the cell i is obtained from the expression

$$f_i(\tau) = \frac{1}{T - \tau + 1} \sum_{t=0}^{T-\tau} \mathbf{v}_t^i \cdot \mathbf{v}_{t+\tau}^i$$

where \mathbf{v}_t^i denotes the velocity of cell i at time t and T is the total time of the simulation/experiment. This function when averaged over all cells predicts the probability that a cell moving at time t in the direction of \mathbf{v} will move in a similar direction at time $t + \tau$. Thus, we have two ways of testing the model, first, we compare the video outputs, next, to be more quantitative, we calculate the velocity autocorrelations for the model and the experiments.

VACF = average of $f_i(\tau)$ over all cells i as a function of τ

Figure 3. The figure on the left shows the average velocity autocorrelation function obtained from simulations of 200 particles averaged over 100 numerical experiments. The plot on the right shows the

same quantity calculated from the trajectories of 50 cells observed and tracked using the digital images of a single experimental video.

The interpretation of the plots is as follows: until the cells have a preferable direction of motion (towards the source of the chemoattractant) the velocity autocorrelation is close to one. As soon most of the cells get close to the source (after some characteristic time in the range of 30 time units) they loose orientation and start to move in random directions around the location of the maximum of the chemoattractant concentration.

The analogous time dependence of the above functions provides a further support for the applicability of our modelling method. The videos and the quantitative analysis of the velocities supports that the behaviour of the simulated cells is similar to those observed in the experiments. Thus, we have reason to claim that the essential features of the biological process of neutrophil swarming have been appropriately accounted for within our modelling approach.

Code

The .py and .ipynb files used to simulate neutrophil swarming are available on Zenodo, the title of the corresponding entries being “Code running the computational model for neutrophil swarming”